

Onboarding in SPLs: Challenges and Strategies

INTERVIEW INFORMATION

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Dear participant:

We are Raul Medeiros, Arantza Irastorza, Maider Azanza and Oscar Díaz, researchers from the **Onekin** group at the *University of the Basque Country* (UPV/EHU) and we are working on the onboarding problem applied to *Software Product Lines (SPL)*. The aim of our research is to try to analyse the difficulties encountered by a developer who joins an SPL development team and how this onboarding affects both the person who joins and the rest of the team and the company in general.

As a first phase of this work, we would like to learn about real experiences of companies that have incorporated new developers into their SPL. Specifically, we would like to know the barriers that have been faced and the strategies that have been used to minimise their impact on onboarding. This will allow us to extract and quantify the parameters that influence the onboarding process, and in the future, as a final objective, to develop tools to help improve the process for all the stakeholders involved.

In the search for real experiences, before starting to apply more extensive or exhaustive techniques or tools, we have decided to make personal contacts with local companies that can give us first-hand opinions and sensations. We have looked for companies that are close to us, that are software developers and that have faced the problem of variability in their product portfolio. At this point, we would like to clarify certain concepts. A software product line is a family of software products that have common functionality, but also have a part of the functionality that is variable, i.e. that differs from one product to another according to the specificities of each customer. Therefore, it is the variability in the products what is important, and in our research we are interested in the experience in dealing with this variability, the term "software product line" is of less importance. Different strategies are also applied in the development of these products with variability. Some of them focus on separating the development of the common core (also known as platform) of all products on the one hand, and on the other hand, the development of the specific functionality of each product or final application. The former is called Domain Engineering, and the latter Application Engineering. Often the developers of the Common Core team come from the product development team and its variability, and it is these additions that we are trying to study. However, in this first contact we do not want to restrict ourselves only to experiences that apply this strategy; we are interested in all those that have incorporated developers to their work teams for the implementation of the common core. We have therefore decided to conduct an interview with you **to find out about your experience with the incorporation of developers into the SPL.**

The interview will last about 60 minutes, in which our questions will be aimed at gathering your experience in the onboarding process, ideas for improvement, etc. Please see the attached document for a script of the interview. Two of us will participate in this interview, and with your consent, we will record the session, so that we can analyse it later and draw better conclusions.

By collaborating in this project and if you request it, you will have at your disposal all the information related to the results obtained in this project once it has finished. We commit ourselves to send you possible publications or prototypes of tools that result from this work.

The personal data you provide will be processed anonymously, using an anonymised code to identify each company. They will only be included in the UPV/EHU reference file "*Onboarding SPLs Interviews*" and will only be used for the purposes stated. Your participation in this study is voluntary and you may revoke your consent at any time by contacting the researcher and indicating your code, without giving any explanation and without any harm to you. You may also consult, rectify or cancel your data or simply request that we do not use them for a specific purpose of this research by contacting the researcher.

We thank you very much for your cooperation, and we are at your disposal for any questions you may have at the telephone number or e-mail address listed at the top of his document.